

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable D7.4 1st Ethical and Legal Screening Report Public

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Responsible organisation	Cybercrime Research Institute (CRI)
Editor(s)	Gunhild Scheer
Contributor(s)	Gunhild Scheer
Reviewers(s)	Rashel Talukder (PPHS) Michael O'Callaghan (UCD CCI) Ray Genoe (UCD CCI)

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1. Summary

The core focus of this Deliverable D7.4 is to review and evaluate the ethical and legal screening of key documents provided for this review by the CYCLOPES Project Management Office regarding two crucial policies of the project:

Firstly, the compliance of the Online Privacy Policy implemented on the website of the CYCLOPES project is reviewed against the applicable legal and ethical framework of the EU. This review not only requires evaluation of the document entitled “Privacy Policy”, but also the “Cookie Policy” including the “Cookie Banner”, as well as the process for subscribing to the newsletter made available at the CYCLOPES website.

Secondly, the consent forms for events of the CYCLOPES project are reviewed against the applicable legal and ethical framework of the EU. This review requires an evaluation of the “Information Sheet” and the “Informed Consent Form” used for participation in CYCLOPES practitioner workshops, as well as the “Informed Consent Form” for participation in CYCLOPES events and processing of personal data.

It should be noted that this is not a final legal assessment or a legal compliance report but merely identifies potential problem areas to allow for further review. The review does not take national law into account.

2. Introduction

The CYCLOPES project aims to build and maintain an innovation-driven law enforcement network facilitating their combat against cybercrime. The exchange of information and experiences of the participants in the fight against cybercrime represents the projects core topic.

2.1. Overview

The DoA describes Task 7.1 as relevant for this deliverable as follows:

“Task 7.1 - Legal and Ethical Issue Guidance to Consortium Partners During Project Implementation

The goal of this task is to provide the necessary guidance to the consortium partners, to allow each to conduct project activities in accordance to legal and ethical regulations. This work includes the development of data protection templates as well as actionable ethical and legal guidance that will support consortium members during the process of carrying out work and preparing deliverables. Moreover, for the topics and deliverables that are considered as potential ethical and legal risks, the team will scrutinise the deliverables and support authors to adhere to compulsory guidelines.”¹

The outcome of Task 7.1 includes an Ethical and Legal Screening Report assessing the ethical and legal screening of selected deliverables, which will be continued in Deliverable D7.5 towards the end of the CYCLOPES project. The Ethical and Legal Screening Report has been included in the Project Management Manual as a detailed description of ethical and legal issues, especially with regard to full data protection in all data processing activities in and for the CYCLOPES project. It thus represents the first edition.

The key objective of this Deliverable D7.4 is to analyse and assess the ethical and legal screening of the following key documents which have been selected for this review by the CYCLOPES Project Management Office in May 2023²: (1) Privacy Policy, (2) Cookie Policy, (3) Information Sheet, (4) Consent Form, and (5) Informed Consent Form. While the Privacy Policy and the Cookie Policy are made available on the website of the CYCLOPES project, the Information Sheet and the Consent Form are used for participation in practitioners' workshops and the Informed Consent Form is used for participation in events of the CYCLOPES project and the related processing of personal data.

The ethical and legal review of these key documents in this Deliverable D7.4 aims to provide guidance to all partners of the CYCLOPES Consortium for achieving ethical and legal compliance.

2.2. Methodology

The CYCLOPES consortium is committed to ensuring that all activities within the CYCLOPES project are legally compliant and within the applicable ethical framework in order to build the necessary trust within this law enforcement network.

¹ DoA, Task T7.1, p. 37.

² CYCLOPES Project Management Office, mail of 17 May 2023.

Even though there is a high degree of fragmentation in societal, ethical and legal standards across the entire European Union concerning activities of LEAs, the key documents reviewed in this Deliverable D7.4 pertain to areas in which the European Union has undertaken effective approaches to harmonise the legislative framework. As a consequence, the main legal framework regarding privacy and data protection consists predominantly of the GDPR and the ePrivacy Directive.

2.3. Structure

This deliverable includes the following chapters:

- *Chapter 1* presents the executive summary of this deliverable D7.4.
- *Chapter 2* provides an overview and the methodology of the approach to this deliverable D7.4 as an introduction.
- *Chapter 3* reviews and evaluates the compliance of the CYCLOPES website's Privacy Policy with the applicable legal framework in the EU.
- *Chapter 4* reviews and evaluates the legal screening of the CYCLOPES project's consent forms for project events with the applicable legal framework in the EU.
- *Chapter 5* presents a brief summary and evaluation of the assessment provided in this deliverable D7.4 and points out key elements of full ethical and legal aspects to all partners of the CYCLOPES Consortium.

3. Review and Evaluation of Online Privacy Policy

One advantage of establishing an online presence for the CYCLOPES project is that it provides easy access to the targeted audiences, not only raising interest among the cybercrime threat community but also beyond in civil society in general. The CYCLOPES website is the primary channel to support communication and dissemination of project information and results.³ The communication and dissemination plan outlined in deliverable D6.1 for the CYCLOPES project's website aimed to ensure that the website adheres to the relevant legal framework by including the following provisions:

"A link to the privacy policy will be provided as a pop-up banner to the users to read before accessing the website. This will inform the user of the data we gather, any tracking performed and the cookie policy. The user will have the choice to continue using the site under the set conditions or navigate away.

*An agreement policy will be prepared and the visitors will be informed on the reasons the website collects any information and how this information will be used, as in the case with newsletter subscriptions, contact forms and registration to platforms."*⁴

When opening the project's website at www.cyclopes-project.eu, a pop-up banner appears inviting any visitor to "accept" the "Cookie Policy". A hyperlink takes the visitor to the Cookie Policy, which is permanently available at www.cyclopes-project.eu/cookie-policy.⁵ The CYCLOPES website also makes permanently available a "Privacy Policy" at www.cyclopes-project.eu/privacy-policy and offers visitors at any stage either to subscribe to a newsletter (in the upper level of CYCLOPES website's footer) or to join the CYCLOPES network. From a legal perspective, these five elements all together constitute for a visitor the privacy policy established for the CYCLOPES website and are part of the overall CYCLOPES online privacy policy. For that reason, the legal compliance of all five elements is reviewed and evaluated in turn in the light of the project's Dissemination and Communication Plan:

- Cookie Banner (section 3.1 below);
- Cookie Policy (section 3.2 below);
- Privacy Policy (section 3.3 below);
- Newsletter Subscription Process (section 3.4 below); and
- Contact Form and Joining CYCLOPES Network Process (section 3.5 below).

³ Section 6.1.1 of Deliverable D6.1, p. 22.

⁴ Section 6.1.1.3 of Deliverable D6.1, p. 25.

⁵ When a laptop user visited the CYCLOPES website on June 29, 2023, they found that the term "Cookie Policy" was not linked to www.cyclopes-project.eu/cookie-policy, but the hyperlink to the Cookie Policy was present when the CYCLOPES website was accessed from a smartphone on August 4, 2023.. For this review it is assumed that the Cookie Banner provides a hyperlink to the Cookie Policy.

3.1. Review of Cookie Banner

Upon opening the CYCLOPES websites for the first time, the Cookie Banner appears and invites the visitor to follow the link to the Cookie Policy and to agree with the Cookie Policy by clicking the button “Accept” provided in the Cookie Banner. According to the e-Privacy Directive and the GDPR, the appearance of a so-called Cookie Banner is required when optional cookies are set on a website.⁶ Depending on the device with which the CYCLOPES website is accessed, the Cookie Banner blocks the view at approximately 25% of the lower screen. Above the button “Accept”, the Cookie Banner displays the following text:

“By using this site, you agree to our [Cookie Policy](#). Please note that we only use essential functional cookies and anonymous statistical cookies, which means that we do not retain any personal information. Similarly, no advertising agencies will have access to your browsing data.”

The website user does not have the option to choose between "technically necessary" cookies and accepting all cookies through a second button, nor is there a button available to reject all non-necessary cookies. However, the cookies actually set on the website are:

- four Google Analytics cookies (to store and count page views, to calculate visitor, session and campaign data and **track** site usage for the site’s analytic report. The duration of these cookies varies between one minute (**storage of the users ID**) a day and one year one month and four days.)
- one "other" cookie,
- one performance cookie,
- and a single technically necessary cookie.

Hence, the cookie banner's assertion that only statistical and essential functional cookies have been set appears dubious, as it contradicts the actual situation: two of the Google Analytics cookies (storage of the user ID and tracking cookie that recognizes unique visitors) may not be classified as purely statistical or essential functional cookies. The setting of these third-party cookies requires the user’s consent in some EU Member States, if these are not functionally necessary.⁷

In addition, the question arises whether the cookie banner with the indication that the further use of the website is considered as consent, legally stands. The ECJ ruled that consent must be given clearly and actively for the specific case and without any doubt (Art. 4 No. 11 GDPR). The passive, non-ticking of a checkbox does not constitute an effective act of consent.⁸ Applied to websites, the ECJ ruled that the consent banners "We use cookies - if you continue to use our website, you consent to the use of cookies" that have been frequently used to date are not sufficient. The continued use of a website does not constitute clear and unequivocal consent for the specific case of cookie use. The reference of the banner therefore seems not to lead to

⁶ Cookies, the GDPR, and the e-Privacy Directive; see: <https://gdpr.eu/cookies/>.

⁷ “Is Google Analytics GDPR Compliant?”, Lubowicka, 31.08.2023; see: <https://piwik.pro/blog/is-google-analytics-gdpr-compliant/>.

⁸ JUDGMENT OF THE COURT (Grand Chamber), 1 October 2019: see: <https://curia.europa.eu/juris/document/document.jsf?mode=DOC&pageIndex=0&docid=218462&part=1&doclang=EN&text=&dir=&occ=first&cid=2004106>.

an effective consent of the website visitor according to Art. 4 No. 11 GDPR and Art. 7 (4) GDPR.

However, the cookies actually set on the website are four Google Analytics cookies, one "other" cookie, one performance cookie and a single technically necessary cookie. For this reason, the information of the banner also seems questionable. This would be another reason why consent could not be effectively given because the reference in the banner itself does not correspond to the facts. The cookie banner also claims that the cookies set "*do not retain any personal information*". This seems to be questionable too, because one of the Google Analytics cookies stores the unique user ID of the website's visitor. The definition of personal data of Art. 4 (1) GDPR is the following: "personal data" means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an **identification number**, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person..."⁹

Related to the Google Analytics cookie on the Cyclopes project website which stores the users unique ID, the second declaration of the Cookie-Banner that no personal data is retained is also debatable. The user ID is suited to identify the visitor of the website. In conjunction with the cookie of Google Analytics, which tracks site usage and can recognise individual users, the identifiability of the visitor seems to be well possible. These two cookies may not be qualified as only statistical evaluation cookies.

The fact that the Cookie-Banner on the website of the CYCLOPES project contains inaccurate information should be reconsidered as soon as possible. The same applies to the setting of cookies. It should be possible for visitors of the website (who come from various EU Member States) to effectively consent to optional cookies or to reject them without being prevented from using the website.

It should be noted that a large number of website operators in the EU, who have not given users the option of selecting cookies or giving their effective consent, have now been successfully warned and fines amounting to millions have been imposed.¹⁰ Continuing to operate the Cyclopes website with cookies that may require consent represents a risk for the Cyclopes project that should not be underestimated.

Furthermore, the fact that a large part of the site's visitors are educated in law may lead to a reduction of trust in the whole project, which is also dedicated to legal issues.

It's important to reiterate that legal screening does not encompass the specific national legislations of each country. In certain cases, some EU Member States might have different legal requirements for setting cookies compared to others within the EU. This review therefore

⁹ See: <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-4-gdpr/>.

¹⁰ Cookies equally easily accepted or refused: "the CNIL sends a second series of orders to comply", 23 July 2021; see: <https://www.cnil.fr/en/cookies-equally-easily-accepted-or-refused-cnil-sends-second-series-orders-comply>; "noyb files 422 formal GDPR complaints on nerve-wrecking "Cookie Banners" ", see: <https://noyb.eu/en/noyb-files-422-formal-gdpr-complaints-nerve-wrecking-cookie-banners>.

makes no claim to completeness and conclusive accuracy, but merely encourages those responsible for the website to address the problems.

3.2. Review of Cookie Policy

The Cookie Policy is made permanently available at www.cyclopes-project.eu/cookie-policy. It seems to provide all mandatory and helpful information concerning cookies potentially placed on a visitor's device when using the CYCLOPES website.

3.2.1. Part of an Overall "Privacy Policy"

After a standard definition of what cookies are, the Cookie Policy explains offers the visitor under its first sub-heading¹¹ to either contact the data protection officer of PPHS or to "*read more about our privacy policy*" in the Privacy Policy. This wording seems to suggest to a visitor that the Cookie Policy is part of a wider "*privacy policy*". However, the visitor is sent searching "*the footer of the website*" for further information. Especially when the Cookie Policy and the Privacy Policy together create a single overall "*privacy policy*", then these policies should include direct hyperlinks to each other. Furthermore, the Cookie Policy and the Privacy Policy should supplement each other in providing mandatory information to visitors.

3.2.2. Definition of "We"

Under the second sub-heading¹² the Cookie Policy contains a definition of any reference to "we", which appears to match the meaning of "we" used in the Privacy Policy which neither offers a definition of "we" nor even refers to the explanation provided in the Cookie Policy. Especially when both policies are intended to create one single overall "*privacy policy*" together, then it seems recommendable to extend the definition of "we" provided in the Cookie Policy to the Privacy Policy.

The definition of "we" is then translated into "*legal terms*" by presenting PPHS as the controller responsible for the processing of personal data "*occurring on the website*" including the use of cookies. This explanation appears too narrow because the data processing for which a controller is responsible pursuant to Art. 24 GDPR, does not solely "*occur on the website*". Rather, such data processing is enabled via the website because, for example, direct marketing campaigns run with the personal data acquired from this website do not "*occur on the website*".

The offer to address PPHS and/or its data protection officer with any question, request or issue concerning the protection of personal data refers further explanations "in the policy" without specifying which policy is referred to. This could be only the Privacy Policy or only the Cookie Policy or both, or even the overall "*privacy policy*" alluded to earlier, but the visitor is left guessing and, therefore, the phrase is too ambiguous.

¹¹ The first sub-heading is "WHAT IF THIS COOKIE POLICY DOES NOT ANSWER ALL OF YOUR QUESTIONS?".

¹² The second sub-heading is "WHO ARE "WE"?".

3.2.3. The Cookies Used at CYCLOPES Website

Under the third sub-heading¹³ the Cookie Policy first provides a more detailed technical explanation of cookies.

The rather minor irritation by the term “*the User*” is later intensified in the description provided for “*anonymised statistical cookies*”. In this description it is stated that “*we use the anonymisation feature of google analytics to anonymise your IP address immediately after collection. See point 5 for more information.*” This is a clear indication that the CYCLOPES website uses “*google analytics*”, but the Cookie Policy does not provide the legal basis for using the services of this “*third-party provider*”. Further, it seems to remain uncertain whether “*Google Analytics*” is the only “*third-party provider*” whose “*anonymised statistical cookies*” are used. In fact, there is one more third-party provider: Amazon Web Services. This third-party provider is not mentioned in the Cookie Policy. In addition, the reference “*for more information*” appears to be misleading because there is no designated “*point 5*” because the sections of the Cookie Policy are not numbered. According to the Cookie Policy’s section “*With Whom Do We Share Your Data?*” (the 4th capitalised sub-heading), Google Analytics is one of the third-party providers “*who help us process your data*”. The term “*your data*” seems to imply the processing of a user’s personal data which is not anonymised.

3.2.4. Strictly Necessary Cookies and “Join us” Process

The Cookie Policy defines strictly necessary cookies as “*essential for the operation of the Site*”. By way of example, this definition refers to cookies placed on a visitor’s device in order to “*identify registered users*”. However, the CYCLOPES website does not seem to offer any login for “*registered users*”. The process for registering participation in an event could not be tested for this review because no events were open at the time of review. As a result for this review, the CYCLOPES website did not include any need to “*identify registered users*” and “*ensure they can access the website*”. As explained above, the website sets only one necessary cookie, which Amazon Services provide. However, this is not mentioned specifically at all in the Cookie Policy.

The only process that appears as a registration is the process “*join us*” for joining the CYCLOPES network¹⁴ which requires a visitor to fill in a form, but clicking the button “*Join Cyclopes*” then merely sends a message possibly to the controller and prompts the visitor in a green banner on the screen with the text: “*Thank you for your message. It has been sent*”¹⁵. In addition, the process to “*Join Cyclopes*” is neither safeguarded by a double opt-in procedure nor leads to a confirmation mail sent to the e-mail address provided for joining. The results in an inability to prove that the mail address provided in the “*join us*” process actually belongs to a visitor wanting to join. Such inability exposes the PPHS as the controller of the CYCLOPES website unnecessarily to potential litigation about sending mails to people without their consent (spam) in breach of Art. 6(1) GDPR and Art. 13 ePrivacy Directive.

3.2.5. Functionality Cookies

The Cookie Policy explains functionality cookies as cookies for saving a visitor’s preferences “*for helpful features, such as providing the Site in a different language*”. At the time of the review however, the CYCLOPES website did not seem to offer the option anywhere to see

¹³ The third sub-heading is „WHICH COOKIES DO WE USE AND WHY?“.

¹⁴ The online process of joining the CYCLOPES network is reviewed in detail in section 3.5 below.

the website in any other language than English. In addition, the CYCLOPES website did not appear to offer visitors any other optional user preferences. Therefore, the visitor is left guessing what functionality cookies might be placed on the visitor's device. Another cookie also set by Amazon Services is an application load balancer cookie, also called a performance cookie. This cookie improves the function of the website. In the Cookie Policy it is not mentioned.

3.2.6. Marketing Cookies

Under the heading "*marketing cookies*", the Cookie Policy defines "*targeting cookies*" as helpful in "*providing users with adverts that are relevant to them by collecting information about their browsing habits and Site usage*". Furthermore, such "*targeting cookies*" are described as enabling "*third parties to display relevant and personalised ads to users*". The visitor is neither informed who these third parties are, nor learns about a process how such third parties may get involved. In addition, the possibility of displaying "*relevant and personalised ads*" gives rise to the connotation that such third party advertisement usually involves generating revenue which could conflict with the purposes of an EU Horizon 2020 research project.

3.2.7. Social Media Cookies

The Cookie Policy defines social media cookies as enabling a visitor's interaction with social media "*such as Facebook and Instagram*". This definition of social media cookies seems to be equivalent to what is commonly referred to as a social media plugin. From an ethical perspective, it would seem like common courtesy to inform the visitor about all social media plugins which are actually placed on the CYCLOPES website. In the course of the review, no social media plugin of Facebook or of Instagram could be found on the CYCLOPES website. Rather, social media plugins for LinkedIn and Twitter were placed in the footer of the CYCLOPES websites.

3.2.8. Consent for "Statistics Cookies"

After these definitions, the Cookie Policy states that "*For the statistics cookies listed above, we require your prior consent*". The term "*statistics cookies*" appears quite ambiguous because it may refer to "*performance cookies*" or to "*anonymised statistical cookies*". The visitor is then informed that such consent can be provided "*by clicking the OK button in the cookie banner and continuing to use the website*". As pointed out in section 3.1 above, the Cookie Banner of the CYCLOPES website does not have an "OK" button, but offers a button to "*Accept*". Although the meaning of either button is essentially similar, the label of this button actually used in the Cookie Banner should be referred to correctly.

Furthermore, the ability to give consent includes the ability to withhold and decline consent. However, the Cookie Banner only offers the button to "*Accept*". It has to be pointed out that no "*statistics cookies*" whatsoever may be placed on the device of a visitor "*continuing to use the website*" without (ever) clicking the "*Accept*" button. Unfortunately, the cookies are not specified here either. In addition, it is pointed out that "*statistics cookies*" require consent, which was supposedly granted by the banner. The insufficient information of the banner and the continued use of the website mistakenly to be interpreted as consent are repeated here.

3.2.9. Data Sharing Partners

Under the fourth sub-heading¹⁵, the Cookie Policy states that personal data collected from visitors is shared within the “*CYCLOPES consortium and those involved in the management of the website, as well as the service providers who help us process your data*”. The Cookie Policy neither defines the term “*CYCLOPES consortium*” nor explains who is “*involved in the management of the website*” or who the helping “*service providers*” are and what data protection measures have been arranged with any of these third parties for the protection of visitor’s personal data.

Pursuant to Art. 13 (1)(e) GDPR, the visitor has to be informed about all recipients or all categories of recipients of the personal data. The phrases referring to the helping “*service providers*” and the involvement “*in the management of the website*” seem to describe categories of recipients, but ultimately remain too ambiguous because no criteria are provided either for the involvement “*in the management of the website*” or for helping to process the visitors’ data. The example of “*Google Analytics*” as a supporting “*service provider*” with whom visitors’ data are shared, triggers questions regarding a transfer of visitors’ data into a third country, despite the European Commission’s recent adequacy decision regarding the level of data protection in the USA.¹⁶

In comparison, the term “*CYCLOPES consortium*” indicates a specific recipient or group of recipients but remains without any link or explanation. Therefore, this information provided in the Cookie Policy does not seem to meet with the requirement of a concise, transparent and intelligible form established in Art. 12(1) sentence 1 GDPR.

3.2.10. Data Retention

Under the fifth sub-heading,¹⁷ the Cookie Policy explains that, immediately after collecting the visitors’ data, the “*anonymisation features of Google Analytics*” are used to ensure that “*any information collected via cookies is anonymised*”. This explanation conflicts with the five types of cookies defined under the third sub-heading which are apparently placed on a visitor’s device when using the CYCLOPES website. If “*any information collected via cookies*” was indeed immediately anonymised after collection, then neither functionality cookies, nor marketing cookies, nor social media cookies would make sense to be placed. Therefore, it seems necessary to specify more precisely how anonymisation is achieved for which data collected.

The Cookie Policy alerts the visitor to those “*statistics cookies above, especially the `_ga` and `_gid` cookies, remain on your device for the whole duration of the indicated lifespan*”. This phrase contains three unexplained terms for the visitor that do not meet the standard required in Art. 12(1) GDPR: (i) as in the context of consent, the term “*statistics cookies*” appears uncomfortably ambiguous because it may refer to “*performance cookies*” or to “*anonymised statistical cookies*” or both; (ii) the two specific types of cookies (“*the `_ga` and `_gid` cookies*”) are solely mentioned in this paragraph without any further explanation; and (iii) the phrase “*the*

¹⁵ The fourth sub-heading is “WITH WHOM DO WE SHARE YOUR DATA?”.

¹⁶ European Commission, Commission Implementing Decision of 10 July 2023 pursuant to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the adequate level of protection of personal data under the EU-US Data Privacy Framework, C(2023) 4745 final, available at: https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2023-07/Adequacy%20decision%20EU-US%20Data%20Privacy%20Framework_en.pdf.

¹⁷ The fifth sub-heading is “HOW LONG DO WE KEEP YOUR DATA?”.

indicated lifespan” has no point of reference in the Cookie Policy and the visitor left guessing the “*lifespan*” of what might be addressed as well as where this may have been “*indicated*”.

In addition, the Cookie Policy refers the visitor “*to point 3 for more information on how to delete cookies*”, even though there is no “point 3” designated in the Cookie Policy because its sections are not numbered.

3.2.11. Rights of the Data Subject

Under the seventh sub-heading,¹⁸ the Cookie Policy alerts the visitor to the rights of the data subject according to Art. 15 – 21 GDPR and emphasises that the any “*personal data processed through cookies*” are anonymised immediately after collection. This contrasts again to the elaborate description of the five different types of cookies placed on a visitor’s device when using the CYCLOPES website. If all “*personal data processed through cookies*” were indeed anonymised immediately after collection, then neither functionality cookies, marketing cookies, or social media cookies would seem to make any sense. Therefore, it appears necessary to specify more precisely how the cookies relate to the anonymisation of the personal data collected.

3.2.12. Conclusion

In summary, it must be pointed out that the Cookie Policy of the CYCLOPES website, on the one hand, does not take into account the facts, namely the cookies actually set, and, on the other hand, provides information that is unrelated and superfluous to the website and its possible uses. It is therefore recommended to revise the Cookie Policy in accordance with the usability of the site, giving comprehensive and transparent information to the cookies that are actually set.

¹⁸ The seventh sub-heading is „WHICH RIGHTS DO YOU HAVE WITH REGARD TO YOUR DATA?“.

3.3. Review of Privacy Policy

The Privacy Policy is made permanently available at www.cyclopes-project.eu/privacy-policy and seems intended to provide all mandatory and helpful information concerning the protection of the personal data of visitors using the CYCLOPES website.

3.3.1. Controller and “We”

Under the first sub-heading,¹⁹ the Privacy Policy informs the visitor properly about the controller responsible for any processing of personal data and then explains as goal to communicate *“how we collect and process your personal data”*. The reference to “we” is not defined, and therefore, the identity of “we” (and “us” later) remains too ambiguous even though PPHS is named as controller in both of the preceding paragraphs. It would seem more useful to provide a definition of “we” which would leave no doubt about who is being referred to as “we”, i.e. *“we as the Controller”*. Otherwise “we” could also include all third party recipients of the personal data collected.

3.3.2. Purposes of Processing

Under the fourth sub-heading,²⁰ the Privacy Policy lists the purposes for which the personal data of visitors is processed in six bullet points; the last of which refers to the purpose *“to answer the questions received via the contact form, when you contact us through the contact form”*. This purpose appears to be too specific in scope. The personal data would also be processed if the contact form was used for comments or any other remarks that are not “questions”. Having actively filled in the contact form and sent the personal data to the Controller, the visitor’s consent pursuant to Art. 6(1)(a) GDPR would also stand as the legal basis for processing the data.

3.3.3. Recipients and Processors

Under the fifth sub-heading,²¹ the Privacy Policy defines the recipients of visitors’ personal data as *“entities which support us in provision of services, such as partners of the consortium ...”*. While the criterion of supporting *“us in the provision of services”* appears extremely wide and insufficiently specified, the list of examples could still narrow the number of entities sufficiently down. However, this is the first and only time the term *“consortium”* appears in this Privacy Policy and the visitor, therefore, cannot understand this reference. To avoid leaving visitors guessing, this term could be capitalised (= “Consortium”) and the second paragraph could include a proper definition in brackets: *“... Commission (Consortium).”*

If there was a semantic difference between *“partners of the consortium”* (first paragraph under the fifth sub-heading) and *“members of the project”* (second paragraph under the fifth sub-heading), then the term *“partners of the Consortium”* would have to be defined here. Otherwise, both paragraphs should use the same phrase, for the avoidance of any doubt, about who receives the personal data.

¹⁹ The first sub-heading is „INFORMATION ABOUT THE CONTROLLER“.

²⁰ The fourth sub-heading is „PURPOSES OF PROCESSING“.

²¹ The fifth sub-heading is „RECIPIENTS AND PROCESSORS“.

3.3.4. Data Retention

Under the sixth sub-heading,²² the Privacy Policy informs the visitor that personal data processed on the basis of consent “*will be processed until it is withdrawn*”. Similarly, the visitor is informed that personal data is processed for direct marketing “*until the objection referred to below is submitted*”. Both phrases seem to clash with the principle of data minimisation established in Art. 5(1) (c) GDPR. According to the principle of data minimisation, the period of processing solely depends on the purpose for which the data have been provided and are being processed.

3.3.5. The Right to Data Portability

Under the seventh sub-heading,²³ the Privacy Policy lists in seven bullet points the rights of the data subject under GDPR. The sixth bullet point refers to the right to “*transfer your personal data*”. The phrase “*transfer your personal data*” seems to refer to the right to data portability pursuant to Art. 20 GDPR, but does not properly express this right because a “*right to transfer*” may simply be the consequence of having accessed the personal data and does not require a particular format of the personal data.

In addition, only the second part of the right to data portability (the right to transmit personal data) appears to be mentioned in the phrase “*transfer your personal data*”. Before a data subject can “*transfer*” or “*transmit*” their personal data to another controller, the data subject has to receive their personal data in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format. Therefore, the right to data portability of Art. 20 (1) GDPR comprises the data subject’s right to receive their data (in a common format!) as well as the data subject’s right to transmit that data.

The right to data portability concerns a triangular relationship (current controller, data subject, new controller), so that the term “transfer” appears inaccurate. The term “transfer” commonly refers to a two-person relationship. Although the data subject has the right to have the personal data transmitted directly from one controller to another, such direct transmission constitutes an exception and is only possible “where technically feasible”, Art. 20(2) GDPR.

While the effect of exercising the right to data portability may ultimately be that the data subject’s personal data is moved from the current controller to a new controller, the term “transfer” neglects the specifics of the right to data portability, especially in the required common format.

3.3.6. Right to Object

Under the eighth subheading,²⁴ the Privacy Policy informs the visitor about the data subject’s right to objection pursuant to Art. 21 GDPR. According to this explanation, the visitor’s objection stops the processing of the visitor’s personal data unless there are overriding “*important legitimate grounds*” for the processing, or the personal data is needed for “*claims*”. Both of these exceptions appear to fail the requirements set out in Art. 21(1) sentence 2 GDPR. According to Art. 21(1) sentence 2 alternative 1 GDPR, the controller has to demonstrate “*compelling*” legitimate grounds for continuing the processing. Therefore, merely “*important*” legitimate ground would not be sufficient. According to Art. 21(1) sentence 2 alternative 2

²² The sixth sub-heading is “PERIOD OF DATA PROCESSING”.

²³ The seventh sub-heading is “RIGHTS OF THE DATA SUBJECT”.

²⁴ The eighth sub-heading is “OBJECTION”.

GDPR, not just any “*claims*” can justify the continuation of the processing. Rather, only the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims have the capacity to legitimise continuing to process a data subject’s personal data.

In addition, there is ambiguity regarding the processing of personal data for direct marketing purposes which is not even supposed to happen according to the Cookie Banner. According to the Privacy Policy, when visitors object to their data being processed “*for purposes associated with direct marketing*”, the processing of these personal data is stopped “*for this purpose*”. On a strict interpretation of “*this purpose*” the processing of the personal data is only stopped with regard to one specific purpose “*associated with direct marketing*” which the visitor has objected to. If this were the case, then this would infringe Art. 21(3) GDPR which requires the controller to cease processing a data subject’s personal data “*for direct marketing purposes*” (plural!) after the data subject has objected.

3.3.7. International Data Transfer

Under the ninth sub-heading,²⁵ the Privacy Policy informs the visitor that services are used which may involve the transfer of the visitor’s personal data to servers in third countries, and aims to assure the visitor that any such transfer takes place in compliance with the requirements under chapter V. of GDPR in general and Art. 45 and 46 GDPR. However, this assurance does not come across as convincing because it is preceded by the statement “*We do not intend to send your personal data*”.

In contrast to the requirements for data controllers under GDPR, this statement does not present the acting “*we*” (which may or may not be the “*Controller*” defined under the first sub-heading) as sufficiently in control of the processing of personal data. The GDPR expects a controller to take charge and ensure that the processing of personal data is in compliance with GDPR, Art. 24(1) sentence 1 GDPR. In addition and perhaps more important, if transferring personal data to a third country was unintentionally happening, then measures ensuring compliance with Art. 45 and 46 GDPR would seem more than unlikely to have been put in place by the Controller. If a controller intends to transfer personal data to a third country, then the controller has to inform the data subject, in compliance with Art. 13(1)(f) GDPR.

3.3.8. Data Security

In the second paragraph under the tenth sub-heading,²⁶ the Privacy Policy informs the visitor about the measures implemented for data security. However, this information seems somewhat misplaced under the heading “PROFILING” under which a visitor seems more likely to expect information about automated decision-making processes, or the use of cookies, or alternatives like browser-fingerprints. Therefore, it appears recommendable to present the information about data security under a separate sub-heading in the Privacy Policy.

²⁵ The ninth sub-heading is “TRANSFER OF PERSONAL DATA TO THIRD COUNTRIES”.

²⁶ The tenth sub-heading is “PROFILING”.

3.4. Review of Newsletter Subscription Process

In the upper level of its footer, the CYCLOPES website allows visitors to subscribe to a newsletter at any stage. The section for the newsletter subscription is entitled “Subscribe for newsletter” under which the visitor is invited to provide “*Your email address:*” and has to acknowledge the statement “*I confirm/I have read, understood and agree to the Privacy Policy*” before clicking the button “*Send*”. This will cause a green button to appear, displaying the text “*Thanks for subscribing to the newsletter*”.

The subscription of a newsletter is based on consent. In order to avoid legal claims for material and immaterial damages (e.g. pursuant Art. 82(1) GDPR), a controller needs to be able to provide evidence that consent has been provided by the recipient of a newsletter. According to the European Data Protection Board (EDPB), the controller has to document the text, the time and the procedure of the consent in order to show that the data subject had been properly informed before providing their consent (see EDPB, Guidelines 05/2020 of 4 May 2020 on consent under Regulation 2016/679, para. 108).

By merely displaying a green button “*Thanks for subscribing to the newsletter*” on the CYCLOPES website, its Controller neither receives any confirmation of consent from the provided email address (*double-opt-in* procedure), nor simply confirms the subscription to the provided email address (*opt-in* procedure) informing the owner of the email address about the subscription and enabling this owner to react by, e.g., objecting to the subscription or withdrawing the consent. Therefore, the CYCLOPES website’s Controller could be held liable for sending the newsletter to email addresses as spam, where the owner of the email address has not consented to receiving the newsletter.

Against this background, the use of a **double-opt-in procedure** seems recommendable and would involve the following two steps:

- *Firstly*, the controller sends out a confirmation mail to the email address provided in the newsletter subscription form. This confirmation mail informs the owner of the email address that the email address has been provided to the controller for subscription to the newsletter and provides an individualised hyperlink.
- *Secondly*, the recipient of the confirmation mail has to confirm her/his consent to receiving the newsletter by activating an individualised hyperlink.

The *double-opt-in procedure* ensures a double-check with the owner of the e-mail address and ensures that the newsletter is only sent to recipients after they have given their consent.

If a double-opt-in procedure was not implemented for the newsletter subscription, then the use of the simple **opt-in procedure** would be recommended, at the very least, in order to provide at least some evidence that necessary precautions for verifying the subscription of the CYCLOPES newsletter with the owner of the email address have been implemented.

3.5. Review of CYCLOPES Network's Joining Process and Contact Form

The CYCLOPES website offers the visitor, in the right-hand corner of its header, a button “*join us*” for joining the CYCLOPES network at any stage. Clicking this button leads the visitor to a form which is made available at www.cyclopes-project.eu/join-us and requires the visitor to provide in separate boxes the “*Full name*”, the “*Organisation Name*”, the “*Official E-mail*”, the “*Organisation Type*”²⁷ as well as the “*Reason for joining*” and invites the visitor to “*Please provide any additional information – website links, product information, etc.*”.

Much in the same way as the form for joining the CYCLOPES network, the contact form (accessible via the button “*Contact*” in the header and made permanently available under www.cyclopes-project.eu/contact) requires the visitor to provide in separate boxes the “*Full name*”, “*Your E-mail*”, as well as a “*Topic*” and invites the visitor to “*Please enter your message*”.

In both forms, the contact form as well as the form for joining the CYCLOPES network, the visitor also has to actively tick “*I confirm/ I have read, understood and agree to the [Privacy Policy](#)*” before clicking on the button “send message” (contact form) or “*Join Cyclopes*” (“*join us*” form) will prompt the visitor with a green banner on the screen displaying the text: “*Thank you for your message. It has been sent.*”

Both processes, the “*Contact us*” process and the “*Join Cyclopes*” process appear sufficiently safeguarded against receiving email addresses from owners who do not wish to contact CYCLOPES or to join the CYCLOPES network. Sending mails out to such email addresses creates a vulnerability to litigation for unsolicited mails. As a minimum precaution, it would seem recommendable to verify each process with the owner of the email address entered in the form. For this purpose, a state-of-the-art safeguard would be the *double opt-in procedure* and, though to a lower degree, an *opt-in procedure* sending at least a confirmation mail to the e-mail address provided in the respective form. The lack of implementing any such safeguards results in an inability to prove that the email address provided in the “*join us*” process actually belongs to a somebody wanting to join.

Just like in the case of the newsletter subscription process²⁸, this inability exposes the PPHS as the controller of the CYCLOPES website unnecessarily to potential litigation about sending mails to people without their consent (spam) in breach of Art. 6(1) GDPR and Art. 13 ePrivacy Directive.

Against this background, preferably the implementation of a *double-opt-in process*, but failing that the implementation of an *opt-in process* as a minimum seems also highly recommendable for the process of contacting CYCLOPES and the process of joining the CYCLOPES network. Both, the *double-opt-in process* as well as the *opt-in process* are described in more detail in section 3.4 above.

²⁷ The “*Organisation Type*” can be selected from a drop down menu offering either one of the five specific types of organisation “*LEA*”, “*Industry*”, “*Academic Research*”, “*Judicial*” and “*Government/Public Body*” or the alternative “*Other*” which prompts the visitor to “*specify the type of organisation*” in an additional box.

²⁸ Section 3.4 above.

4. Review and Evaluation of Consent Forms for Events

The CYCLOPES project aims to create a network of practitioners fighting cybercrime which is in constant dialogue with representatives of industry, academia and policymakers as well as with other practitioner networks. The cooperation and vital exchange of information within this community is encouraged by various events; in particular, workshops, surveys/questionnaires and conferences.²⁹ While practitioner workshops form the very engine of the CYCLOPES project, identifying the capabilities and needs of LEAs in order to define common priorities towards innovations and standardisation,³⁰ annual Joint Live Exercises together with representatives of industry and academia serve as testing ground for selected products and solutions identified by the CYCLOPES market and research observation.³¹

Participation in all of these events involves processing the personal data of each participant. The CYCLOPES project's approach to legal compliance has made it a priority to base this processing of personal data on the participant's proper consent. For this purpose, each participant invited to a CYCLOPES event receives a document providing relevant information concerning data protection compliance ("Information Sheet") as well as a form to fill in in order to provide consent to the processing of their personal data for a practitioner workshop or for another event. These three documents have been elaborated which are reviewed here in turn:

- the "Information Sheet" (section 4.1 below);
- the "Informed Consent Form" used for participation in CYCLOPES practitioner workshops (section 4.2 below) and
- the template "Informed Consent Form" for participation in CYCLOPES events and processing of personal data (section 4.3 below).

4.1. Review of Information Sheet

The Information Sheet is provided to every potential participant when the participant has been invited to a CYCLOPES event and is intended to provide all relevant information for providing informed consent via the simultaneously provided consent form for participation in CYCLOPES activities. The "Information Sheet" contains general background information about the CYCLOPES project and specific details like time and place of the particular event the participant is invited to. These specific details have to be adjusted for every CYCLOPES event. The information Sheet also has to provide the information mandatory for compliance with GDPR.

4.1.1. Responsibility for Data Processing

The mandatory information under GDPR includes the information about who is the controller of the personal data processed for the event. In this respect, the Information Sheet first provides the following information under its third sub-heading³²:

²⁹ Section 2.1 of Deliverable D5.1, p. 6.

³⁰ Section 6.2.1 of Deliverable D6.1, p. 29.

³¹ Section 6.2.3 of Deliverable D6.1, p. 30.

³² The third sub-heading is "What will you need to do?".

“All data shall be subject to strict Data Protection as planned for and monitored by the Data Controller, Marcin Golizda from Polish Platform for Homeland Security.”

Under the sixth sub-heading,³³ the Information Sheet then provides the following information for “*when the activity is over*”:

“The responsibility of all information, including the Consent Form, is the organiser and/or the researcher responsible of the workshop (see contact details below).”

This information may appear slightly confusing and somewhat imprecise, especially since the sub-headings of the Information Sheet are not numbered rendering cross-references rather ambiguous.

According to Art. 13 GDPR, the responsibility for the information is allocated to the data controller. The reference to “*the organiser and/or the researcher*” under “*contact details*” seems to imply that the “*organiser*”, the “*researcher*” and the three “*contact persons*” individually named below might be considered as separate or joint controllers pursuant to Art. 26 GDPR. If that was the intended meaning, then it would have to be expressed in a more forward manner especially avoiding the ambiguity caused by the use of “*and/or*”.

A further ambiguity concerns the question of how the two statements regarding responsibility for processing of personal data relate to each other. The reference to the “*contact details below*” in the second statement seems insufficiently precise because it could refer to the details provided under the fourteenth sub-heading³⁴ or under the seventeenth subheading³⁵. Under the seventeenth sub-heading, which contains the phrase “*contact person*”, only the details of three different individuals are provided, while an explanation of their role concerning the processing of personal data is elsewhere. Under the fourteenth sub-heading, the explanation of their role only provided for two individuals.³⁶ This role appears to only be defined for one of individuals as “*Project Data Controller*”, but this capitalisation seems slightly out of sync with the role of the person behind the same email address defined before (in the second paragraph) under the third sub-heading³⁷ as representative of PPHS and “*Data Controller*” (without “*Project*”). The role of the second individual is merely described as “*organiser of this workshop*” – without capitalisation³⁸. Therefore, the role of individual behind this e-mail address does not seem to be clearly defined in the Information Sheet.

4.1.2. Responsibility for Data Processing

Under the seventh sub-heading,³⁹ the Information Sheet assures the participant that the collected personal data is “*kept securely by the researcher/Data Controller*” for the period of the CYCLOPES project plus four additional years afterwards.

The phrase “*researcher/Data Controller*” seems ambiguous because it is not certain whether this might be one and the same person or two different persons. If these were two different persons, then the Information Sheet would have to indicate their role and relationship concerning the processing of personal data. In addition, a “*researcher*” would seem to act most

³³ The sixth sub-heading is “Who will be responsible for all the information when the activity is over?”.

³⁴ The fourteenth sub-heading is “When will you have the opportunity to discuss your participation?”.

³⁵ The seventeenth sub-heading is “Who is the contact person?”.

³⁶ While Marcin Golizda is described as representative of PPHS as “*Project Data Controller*” and Anand Knox is presented as “*organizer of this workshop*”, the role of Rashel Talukder remains unclear.

³⁷ The third sub-heading is “What will you need to do?”.

³⁸ The second individual could be defined either as “*Organiser of this Workshop*” or simply as “*Organiser*”.

³⁹ The seventh sub-heading is “What will happen to the information when the activity is over?”.

likely on behalf of the researcher's organisation which may or may not be a partner of the CYCLOPES Consortium. In this context, the reference to a seemingly individual "researcher" would create an additional uncertainty about what might happen to the personal data in case the individual "researcher" changed job shortly after.

4.1.3. Note on Data Protection Compliance

Under the final sub-heading,⁴⁰ the Information Sheet informs the participant about the notification duties under GDPR, in an effort to assure the participant that any incident is investigated so that measures are taken to prevent it from reoccurring.

This review should probably emphasise that the commitment to inform the participant of "any unexpected data breach" and the corresponding "preventative action" taken exceeds the statutory minimum under GDPR. According to Art. 34(1) GDPR, the controller has the mandatory notification duty to communicate the personal data breach to the data subject. However, this notification is not required under the conditions listed in Art. 34(3) GDPR as exceptions. By indicating that the data subject will be notified in case of any personal data breach – without exception, the Information Sheet creates reasons to trust the CYCLOPES Consortium's commitment to data protection compliance.

4.2. Review of Consent Form for Workshop Participants

Together with the Information Sheet, a participant invited to a CYCLOPES event receives a form entitled "Informed Consent Form". This form requires the participant to either agree or disagree with seven distinct statements concerning participation in the workshop. One of these seven statements requires the participant to provide the following consent:

"I consent to the information collected for the purposes of this activity, once anonymised/ pseudonymised/ de-identified/ de-linked/ (Re)identified (so that I cannot be identified), to be used for any other purposes related to the CYCLOPES project."

In this consent, the phrase "once anonymised/ pseudonymised/ de-identified/ de-linked/ (Re)identified (so that I cannot be identified)" seems rather confusing. If the participant's personal data were properly "anonymised" or "de-identified" or "de-linked", then this data would not constitute personal data any more so that no consent would be required. In contrast to this, if the participant's data were merely "pseudonymised" or "(Re)identified", then this data would still be personal data and the attribution to a specific data subject would still be possible by using additional information which is kept separately, pursuant to the definition of "pseudonymisation" in Art. 4 No. 5 GDPR. Assuming that the text in brackets "(so that I cannot be identified)" describes the result of any of the five types of processing mentioned before, it remains uncertain, therefore, whether any additional information is retained enabling to attribute personal data to the participant as natural person.

⁴⁰ The final sub-heading is "Please note:".

4.3. Review of Consent Form to Processing of Personal Data for Events

The second form submitted for review is the template entitled “*Informed Consent Form for Participation in CYCLOPES <name of the event > and Processing of Personal Data*” (Template).

4.3.1. Right to Data Portability

The second paragraph of the Template lists the rights of the data subject under GDPR and includes a reference to “*the right to transfer data*”. This phrase seems to refer to the right to data portability pursuant to Art. 20 GDPR, but does not properly express this right because the term “*right to transfer data*” seems too broad and includes the personal data of the participant rather accidentally. More importantly, a “right to transfer data” may simply be the consequence of having accessed the data and does not require a particular format of the data.

It seems that only the second part of the right to data portability (the right to transfer the personal data) is addressed in the wording “right to data portability”. A prerequisite for a data subject to be able to “transfer” or “transmit” his or her personal data to another controller is that he or she has received his or her personal data in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format. Therefore, the right to data portability under Art. 20 (1) GDPR includes both the right of the data subject to receive his or her data (in a commonly used format!) and the right to have the data subject transmit that data.

The right to data portability concerns a triangular relationship (current controller, data subject, future controller), so the simple term “transfer” does not quite capture the facts. The term “transfer” rather suggests a two-person relationship. Although the data subject has the right to have the personal data transferred directly from the current controller to a future controller, such a direct transfer is an exception and is only possible “if technically feasible” under Article 20(2) of the GDPR.

While the exercise of the right to data portability may ultimately lead to the transfer of the data subject’s personal data from the current controller to a new controller, the notion of “transfer” neglects the specificities of the right to data portability, in particular the required common format.

4.3.2. Right to Object

The list of the data subject’s rights under GDPR in the second paragraph of this Template also includes a reference to “*the right to object*”. The data subject’s right to object under Art. 21 GDPR also concerns the legal basis for the processing of participant’s personal data by the controller. In contrast to the “*right to withdraw consent*”, the Template does not appear to outline the consequence of having exercised the right to object. The legal consequence and effect of exercising the right to object pursuant Art. 21(1) sentence 2 GDPR is equivalent to the data subject’s right to withdraw consent pursuant to Art. 7(3) sentence 2 GDPR. In both scenarios, the controller’s processing prior to exercising the respective right remains lawful. Against this background, it seems recommendable to clarify more clearly in the Template that the legal consequence and effect of exercising the right is identical for the right to object and the right to withdraw consent.

4.3.3. Making Available to Service Entities

At the end of the Template the following information is provided:

“Personal data may be made available to the entity providing accounting, IT, legal and event services for PPHS.”

Though it is clear why this Template merely refers to the “entity” for “*accounting, IT, legal and event services*”, such entity appears very likely to be known for each CYCLOPES event by the time the participant’s consent is collected. Therefore, this form could indicate not only whether this is one single entity or several entities processing personal data, but also and more importantly explain pursuant to Art. 13(1) lit. a) GDPR who will be the controller of the personal data transferred to these entities because these entities could receive this data either as a separate controller (Art. 24 GDPR), as a joint controller (Art. 26 GDPR) or as a processor (Art. 28 GDPR).

5. Conclusion

This section briefly summarises and evaluates the findings of the analysis and assessment, provided in chapters 3 and 4 above, and highlights key elements for achieving full ethical and legal compliance to all partners in the CYCLOPES Consortium.

This Deliverable D7.4 has reviewed and evaluated the ethical and legal compliance of key documents selected for this screening report from two interconnected areas of the CYCLOPES project:

- *Firstly*, the compliance of the overall online privacy policy implemented at the website of the CYCLOPES project was reviewed against the applicable legal and ethical framework in the EU. This required the analysis and assessment of the following five elements of the CYCLOPES website: the Cookie Banner (section 3.1 above), the Cookie Policy (section 3.2 above), the Privacy Policy (section 3.3 above), the subscription process for the CYCLOPES newsletter (section 3.4 above) and the process for joining the CYCLOPES network as well as the contact form (section 3.5 above).
- *Secondly*, the compliance of the consent forms used for events of the CYCLOPES project is reviewed against the applicable legal and ethical framework in the EU. This required the analysis and assessment of the “Information Sheet” (section 4.1 above) and the “Informed Consent Form” (section 4.2 above) used for participation in CYCLOPES practitioner workshops, as well as the Template entitled “Informed Consent Form” (section 4.3 above) for participation in CYCLOPES events and the processing of personal data.

For ethical and legal compliance, the overall privacy policy of a website needs to inform any visitor about how the visit affects the visitor’s device by placing cookies and which personal data is processed by whom, at what stage and based on which legal basis. The overall online privacy policy presented to visitors of the CYCLOPES website, via the elements assessed in chapter 3 above, addresses all elements necessary for such ethical and legal compliance. Most ambiguities and/or inconsistencies identified in the assessment of this first SEL screening report could easily be rectified by orchestrating the five elements examined in chapter 3 above in greater harmony with each other. This would then translate more accurately what actually happens at technological level in terms of placement of cookies and processing of personal data.

Consent forms are a critical component for the ethical and legal compliance of the interaction with participants of a project’s events. The consent forms used for events of the CYCLOPES project, and assessed in chapter 4 above, provide the core information necessary under EU data protection law. The minor ambiguities identified for each document in the assessment of this first SEL screening report could easily be rectified by adding a little more detail in the respective form. This would then perfect the compliance of these documents with the requirements under GDPR.

Against this background, the documents scrutinised in this first SEL screening report seem very close to full ethical and legal compliance.